

Isis do Vale Meira Lima

📍 Otto-Hahn-Allee, 1, NW1, 28359, Universität Bremen, Bremen, Germany

✉ idovalem@uni-bremen.de | ORCID <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3294-2751>

Lattes Platform: <http://lattes.cnpq.br/5199943129801173>

In 2022, I obtained a B.Sc. in Physics from the Federal University of Ceará (UFC), Brazil, with a focus on Biological Physics and Atomic Force Microscopy. In 2023, I completed an M.Sc. in Physics at the same institution, where my research focused on the microrheology of living cells and the characterization of their viscoelastic properties. Since 2023, I have been a PhD candidate in Physics at the University of Bremen, working as a research assistant at the Institute for Biophysics, with my doctoral studies funded by a CAPES scholarship (Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel, Brazil).

Education

Federal University of Ceará / Department of Physics

02/2018 - 02/2022

Bachelor in Physics

- Title: Study of the distance interaction between cantilever and sample in atomic force microscopy.
- Grantee of: Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico, CNPq, Brazil.
- URL: <http://repositorio.ufc.br/handle/riufc/61014>.

Federal University of Ceará / Department of Physics

03/2022 - 08/2023

Master in Physics

- Title: Determination of viscoelastic properties of living cells from the time-dependent interpretation of Hertz model.
- Grantee of: Coordenação de Aperfeiçoamento de Pessoal de Nível Superior, CAPES, Brazil.
- URL: <http://repositorio.ufc.br/handle/riufc/74172>.

University of Bremen / Institute of Biophysics

10/2023 - 09/2027

PhD in Physics

- Title: 3D biomechanics in confined spaces: from cell to tissue.
- Grantee of: Coordenação de Aperfeiçoamento de Pessoal de Nível Superior, CAPES, Brazil.

Professional Experience

University of Bremen / Institute of Biophysics

Employment: Formal labor contract, Functional Framework: Research assistant, Working hours per week: 30.

04/2024 - 09/2027

Publications

Proteomic analysis of *Cryptostegia grandiflora* latex, purification, characterization, and biological activity of two osmotin isoforms

International Journal of Biological Macromolecules, 2023-12-01 | Journal article

DOI: 10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2023.126529

AUTHORS: Cleverson D.T. Freitas; Diego P. Souza; Thalles B. Grangeiro; Jeanlex S. Sousa; Isis V.M. Lima; Pedro Filho N.

Souza; Cristiano S. Lima; Alexandre D'Emery S. Gomes; Ana C.O. Monteiro-Moreira; Tawanny K.B. Aguiar et al.

2023

Measuring the viscoelastic relaxation function of cells with a time-dependent interpretation of the Hertz-Sneddon indentation model

Heliyon, 2024-05 | Journal article

DOI: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e30623

AUTHORS: I.V.M. Lima; A.V.S. Silva; F.D. Sousa; W.P. Ferreira; R.S. Freire; C.L.N. de Oliveira; J.S. de Sousa.

2024

3D-Printed Structures versus Drilled Cavities: A Comparison of Microconfinement Methods for Rheological Characterization of Multicellular Aggregates

Journal of Molecular Recognition - AFM BioMed 2025 Conference | Journal article

Manuscript submitted, currently under peer review

AUTHORS: Isis V. M. Lima, Chukwuma Chris Muoghalu, Shruti G. Kulkarni, Mènie Wiemer, Jonas Michalewski, Sander van den Driesche, Wiebke Gehlken, Michael J. Vellekoop, and Manfred Radmacher.

2026

Events

- AFM BioMed Conference 2025. Co-cultured aggregates in cylindrical cavities: fibroblasts influence the microenvironment of pancreatic cancer cells. (Talk/Conference).
- Bremen Life Sciences Meeting 2025. Co-cultured aggregates in cylindrical cavities: fibroblasts influence the microenvironment of pancreatic cancer cells. (Meeting).
- Bremen Life Sciences Meeting 2025. Co-cultured aggregates in cylindrical cavities: fibroblasts influence the microenvironment of pancreatic cancer cells. (Meeting).
- Bruker Workshop at AFM BioMed Conference, Barcelona, Spain, 2025. (Workshop).
- Bremen Life Sciences Meeting 2024. Biomechanics of Multicellular Aggregates in 3D Confined Spaces Using Atomic Force Microscopy. 2024. (Meeting).
- Ciência@Apoena. Biomecânica de Tumores em Espaços Confinados. 2024. (Talk/Online).
- German Biophysical Society Meeting, Leipzig, Germany, 22–25 September 2024. Viscoelastic Properties of Mono- and Heterotypic Pancreatic Cancer Aggregates. Event information: <https://dgfb2024.de>. (Poster presentation).
- DPG-Frühjahrstagung der Sektion Kondensierte Materie. Rheology in 3D confined spaces: PANC-1 spheroids on polyHEMA-coated substrates using atomic force microscopy. Berlin, Germany, 2024. <https://www.dpg-verhandlungen.de/year/2024/conference/berlin/part/bp/session/33/contribution/8?lang=en>. (Talk/Conference).
- III Flow cytometry workshop. 2023.
- 9th INFABIC Theoretical-Practical Workshop - Exploring Confocal Microscopy and Nonlinear Optics in the Analysis of Biological Materials. 2021.
- Encontro de Outono da SBF 2021. Ultrasonic pressure waves generated by oscillation of a cantilever in an atomic force microscope. 2021. (Poster/Conference).
- Encontro de Outono da SBF 2020. Effect of proximity with the sample on the vibration spectrum of the cantilever of an atomic force microscope. 2020. (Poster/Conference).
- XXXIV Encontro de Fisicos do Norte e Nordeste. Effect of proximity with the sample on the vibration spectrum of the cantilever of an atomic force microscope. 2019. (Poster/Conference).

Languages

Portuguese	Comprehends Well, Speaks Well, Reads Well, Writes Well.
English	Comprehends Well, Speaks Well, Reads Well, Writes Well.
Spanish	Comprehends Reasonably, Speaks Reasonably, Reads Well, Writes Reasonably.
German	Comprehends Little, Speaks Little, Reads Little, Writes Little.

Complementary Education

I Autumn Course in Scientific Writing. (Timetable: 6h). University of São Paulo, USP, Brazil.	2024 - 2024
German A1.2. (Working hours: 75h). Deutsch und Deutschland Language Institute, SIDD, Brazil.	2023 - 2024
Flow Cytometry Theoretical Course. (Timetable: 4h). UFC Medicines Research and Development Center, NPDM-UFC, Brazil.	2023 - 2023
Theoretical Course of Good Practices in Cell Culture. (Timetable: 20h). Nucleus of Experimental Biology at the University of Fortaleza, NUBEX - UNIFOR, Brazil.	2023 - 2023
7th Electronic and Optical Microscopy Course at UFC Analytical Center. (Timetable: 24h). Federal University of Ceará, UFC, Brazil.	2022 - 2022
HOW TO PUBLISH YOUR RESULTS IN THE PHYSICAL REVIEW JOURNALS. (Timetable: 1h). Brazilian Physics Society, SBF, Brazil.	2021 - 2021
WRITING BETTER SCIENTIFIC PAPERS. (Timetable: 1h). Brazilian Physics Society, SBF, Brazil.	2021 - 2021
Physics of living cells and soft matter (basic). (Timetable: 12h). Federal University of Ceará, UFC, Brazil.	2021 - 2021
Training of Researchers and Writing of High Impact Scientific Papers. (Timetable: 4h). Federal University of São Carlos, UFSCAR, Brazil.	2020 - 2020